

Promoting educational equity: The implementation of translanguaging pedagogy in English language education

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Although the ideology of monolingualism prevails in traditional English language classroom teaching, it is gradually failing to meet the current dynamic landscape of socio-linguistic and socio-cultural diversity. Translanguaging has created more spaces for students to use their varied linguistic and multimodal repertoires to express themselves and enhance learning in actual classroom practices. This paper aims to explore students' perceptions and practices of translanguaging at a university located in southeast China. Data were collected via semi-structured interviews and reflective journals. The study employed qualitative content analysis to investigate the ways in which the establishment of a translanguaging space might facilitate students' access to linguistic and epistemic equity. The paper ends with suggestions and implications regarding the importance of raising students' awareness of translanguaging as a means to embrace all languages, meaning-making resources, and previous knowledge for equitable English language education.

Keywords: Chinese University Students; English Language Education; Equity; Inclusive Education; Translanguaging

1. Introduction

In the current globalised context of linguistic and cultural diversity, English language education is increasingly being found to no longer target the teaching and learning of English per se but rather pay more attention to the ways that enable all English language learners to be equal in voicing and expressing themselves (Fang & Dovchin, 2022; Phyak & De Costa, 2021). However, the current state of English language education is still predominantly characterised by monolingualism and rigid adherence to native speaker norms which are based on the ideology of native-speakerism (Baker & Hüttner, 2019; Cenoz & Gorter, 2011; Holliday, 2005). Inevitably, monolingual approaches with an overemphasis on language priority, and on English language purity in

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particular, have strongly challenged the promotion of inclusiveness and equity in English language education, where people's linguistic, multimodal, and multi-semiotic resources are often marginalised or even ignored (Yao, 2021).

Therefore, various other approaches have been explored to help handle "inequalities that mediate relations between English, English users, and other languages" (Tupas & Rubdy, 2015, p. 7). These approaches advocate for the recognition of the influence of power imbalances inherent in English language education (Han et al., 2016). Among these approaches, translanguaging, whether naturally occurring (spontaneous translanguaging) or explicitly operating (pedagogical translanguaging), has opened up spaces for equitable language education (Chaka, 2024; May, 2014; Motaung, 2024; Nkhi & Shange, 2024).¹ A growing body of studies (Fang & Liu, 2020; Tai, 2022; Tai & Li, 2020; Tai & Wong, 2022) have examined teachers' translanguaging practices and found that the 'affordances', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021a), of translanguaging have the potential to facilitate equity in English language education. However, more studies are still needed, for example, from the perspective of students, to explore the possible ways that translanguaging helps enhance learners' access to equity in today's linguistically and culturally diverse classrooms.

This study begins by reviewing the concept of translanguaging in line with its recent developments. It goes on to provide and analyse empirical data on students' perceptions of language, language usage and language users in the English language classroom—which Salmani Nodoushan (2023) has referred to as a 'petri dish' or a 'panopticon'—to reveal whether the concept of translanguaging is involved and how it can be properly brought in and managed to support linguistic and epistemic equity in English language education. The paper ends by addressing the need for the awareness of equal mindedness towards all individuals and their languages through knowledge acquisition; the importance of translanguaging is also highlighted and relevant implications are provided to help promote linguistic and epistemic equity as well as social and academic inclusion in education.

2. Background

2.1. Conceptualising translanguaging

Translanguaging has been described as a theory of language based on human communication and interaction, a critical and decolonising pedagogy and a political stance (Fang & Xu, 2022; Li, 2018, 2022). The concept of translanguaging was initially coined by Williams (1994) to refer to the pedagogical practice of deliberately alternating between two languages in bilingual classrooms in Wales. García (2009) went on to describe translanguaging as "the act performed by bilinguals of accessing different

linguistic features or various modes of what are described as autonomous languages, in order to maximise communicative potential” (p. 140). In this sense, translanguaging is a practice as well as a pedagogy that involves fluid, flexible and dynamic language usage and opens up spaces to engage and maximise teachers’ and students’ linguistic, multimodal, and multi-semiotic resources in the learning process (Cenoz & Gorter, 2020; Fang & Liu, 2020). Therefore, the original focus of translanguaging was on the language-dependent pedagogical possibilities and innovative spaces that it has created for both teachers and students to exploit all their linguistic resources in the learning process (Lewis et al., 2012; Liu & Fang, 2022).

Li (2018) shaped the term translanguaging in a way to be viewed as a practical theory of language “as a multilingual, multisemiotic, multisensory, and multimodal resource that human beings use for thinking and for communicating thought” (p. 26). On the one hand, this notion offers more evidence of translanguaging as a practical theory of language. It does so by showing that translanguaging transcends socially and politically constructed language systems and structures by seeing language as a multi-dimensional resource and also by incorporating the various cognitive and semiotic resources individuals have available for meaning-making, except for the active use of multiple languages—cf. Salmani Nodoushan (2022). On the other hand, with its focus on individuals and communication rather than language per se, such a notion also indicates that translanguaging can function as a critical and decolonising pedagogy as well as a political project (Li, 2022). Evidence can be found in García’s (2019) argument that as a political stance, translanguaging has “the potential to decolonize our conception of language” (p. 162). Translanguaging is also a transformative process “whereby language users display the best of their creativity and criticality” (Li, 2018, p. 22) as well as their “experiences, subjectivities and agencies” (Li, 2022, p. 175) to challenge and de-naturalise hegemony, hierarchy and normativity associated with languages, language usage and language users. García and Li (2014) argued that translanguaging enables the flow of fluid discourses in various contexts and gives voice to language users’ multiple linguistic identities, especially those that have been marginalised and underestimated.

In general, whether viewed from a pedagogical or theoretical perspective, or as a political or de-colonising stance, translanguaging can serve as an inclusive and comprehensive mechanism for promoting educational equity and social justice (Fang & Xu, 2022; Tian et al., 2022). The promotion of equity and social justice in education requires the integration of students’ full linguistic and multimodal, multi-semiotic resources with their learning opportunities and the inclusion of their linguistic and cultural knowledge (García & Li, 2014). When the concept of translanguaging is introduced and adopted in English language education, it can help equalise the status of all languages in the

classroom by challenging the hegemony of English, recognise and leverage all language users' multiple meaning-making repertoires and resources (García, 2014) and open up spaces for their unique identity construction and negotiation (Flores & García, 2013). In this way, translanguaging can help gain equity and social justice in education through the embrace of linguistic and cultural diversity and by empowering all languages and their learners, especially those language-minoritised students (Fang & Huang, 2023; Yilmaz, 2021).

2.2. Addressing translanguaging

Stakeholders who are committed to equity- and justice-based education have called for the learning environment to become a “‘translanguaging space’, a space for the act of translanguaging as well as a space created through translanguaging” (Li, 2011, p. 1223). A growing body of research has focused on the investigation of how teachers implement pedagogical translanguaging to help enhance students' equal access to language and knowledge construction as well as classroom participation (Fang & Liu, 2020; Rafi & Morgan, 2022; Tai, 2022; Tai & Li, 2020; Tai & Wong, 2022). For example, Tai and Li (2020) conducted a linguistic ethnography to explore how a mathematics teacher created a translanguaging space to jointly negotiate new knowledge with students in an English-medium-instruction (EMI) mathematics classroom in Hong Kong. Their research found that, by transcending modalities and utilising various resources for negotiating meanings, a translanguaging space for co-learning was created to facilitate linguistic and epistemic equity and contribute to more equal and fairer treatment of all language users and their linguistic repertoires in bi/multilingual classrooms. One interesting finding of their study was that teachers' self-positioning as co-learners with their students may contribute to the equalisation of power relations between teachers and students in the classroom. Tai and Li's (2020) findings also resemble the ones reported in Tai (2022), in which the teacher's mobilisation of multilingual, multicultural and multimodal repertoires and resources for meaning-making helped create a translanguaging space for linguistically and culturally diverse students to fairly access language and content learning so as to further promote equity, inclusion and participation in the classroom. Tai (2022) also deemed that translanguaging envisages ideas for the promotion of equity and social justice because it takes into account the entire repertoires of all language users in the classroom (García & Li, 2014).

In addition to investigating translanguaging as an inclusive pedagogical practice in bi/multilingual classroom settings, Tai and Wong (2022) specifically explored the establishment of a translanguaging space by a native English-speaking teacher who had received training in translanguaging. This

study took place in an English as a first language (L1) classroom consisting solely of L1 English students, with the aim of preparing them for living in a multilingual and multicultural society. It observed that translanguaging not only reflects how meanings are constructed through various means, including the use of different available resources, knowledge, and repertoires, but also contributes to the creation of meaningful experiences for all students, enabling them to develop their well-being and identities in today's multilingual and multicultural world. The findings of Tai and Wong's (2022) study demonstrate that translanguaging can be accessible and empowering for all students, allowing them to appreciate the epistemic, linguistic, and cultural diversity in their surroundings. This further supports the notion that translanguaging, as an inclusive pedagogical resource, plays a significant role in promoting social justice and equity in the classroom.

The findings of the studies above highlight the key role of teachers in taking the initiative to create translanguaging spaces to signal students to engage in translanguaging (García & Kley, 2016). However, since translanguaging has been found to be a natural and spontaneous phenomenon among students, rather than a behaviour consciously triggered by teachers through specific pedagogical strategies (Canagarajah, 2013; Cenoz & Gorter, 2017; Fang & Liu, 2020), the pedagogical 'affordances', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021a), of student-led translanguaging in approaching equity in education should also be a focus of research. For example, Fernández (2019) investigated how groupwork interactions characterised by translanguaging served to support culturally and linguistically diverse students' science learning by creating a more equitable science classroom in the Luxembourgish context. Fernández (2019) discovered that through translanguaging, students could activate a display of their own languages, cultures, identities and background knowledge and develop a sense of belonging in their classrooms. In this sense, learning opportunities were ensured for all students because they were offered equal opportunities to create meaning, voice authority and agency, and construct equity in the classroom. In a similar vein, Suárez (2020) explored students' translanguaging practices in a science classroom and found that these practices were either initiated spontaneously by the students themselves or in response to translanguaging cues provided by their teachers. In addition to identifying the subtle influence of teachers' own pedagogical moves and translanguaging practices on students' act of translanguaging, Suárez (2020) found that students leverage multiple linguistic and non-linguistic semiotic resources and repertoires to get engaged in translanguaging practices when constructing and sharing knowledge with their peers and teachers. The study has emphasised the importance of a translanguaging space for creating an equitable learning environment by de-settling normative communicative expectations as well as identifying, valuing and encouraging students to display diverse meaning-

making repertoires and resources. Although Fernández's (2019) and Suárez's (2020) studies were mainly concerned with science education, their findings still provide referential value for English language education, since achieving equity and justice for every learner is a common goal of all education.

Therefore, the aforementioned studies have demonstrated that the practice of translanguaging acknowledges and embraces the flexible use of multilingual, multicultural, multi-semiotic, and multimodal resources and knowledge in the classroom, with the aim of fostering a more inclusive environment that promotes linguistic and epistemic equity. It can be found that previous studies have primarily focused on investigating how teachers incorporate translanguaging as an inclusive pedagogical practice and the subsequent effects on students' learning experience and classroom participation, with the aim of enhancing linguistic and epistemic equity (Fang et al., 2022; Mendoza, 2022; Yilmaz, 2021). Hence, even in cases where translanguaging pedagogy is implemented in English as a medium of instruction (EMI) classrooms, it is primarily initiated by teachers. Therefore, further investigation is required to comprehend how students naturally embrace translanguaging without explicit exposure to bilingual or multilingual pedagogy (Mendoza, 2022).

However, few studies have focused on the pedagogical affordances of students' spontaneous translanguaging by examining how translanguaging is learnt about, responded to, and enforced in English language classrooms. According to Mendoza (2022), such investigations are imperative, since translanguaging can either facilitate or hinder students' own learning or that of others through the mobilisation of all their linguistic and multimodal resources. The concern about translanguaging may stem from the fear that it could be used as an excuse to rely too heavily on the L1 or other languages, which may not be beneficial for expanding the learning outcomes of the target language and content in classrooms. Additionally, many critics of translanguaging have pointed out the vagueness and problematic nature of the concept, as it encompasses a wide range of ideas such as an innate instinct, fluid linguistic practices, a theory and approach to language, and a transformative process, all within a single term (Ballinger et al., 2017; Jaspers, 2018). However, there is currently a lack of empirical evidence to support the theoretical claims associated with translanguaging and its contribution to equity in education (Cummins, 2021). Therefore, investigating translanguaging practices from the students' perspective can thus offer further evidence of, and insights into, the credibility, availability as well as sustainability of translanguaging for the promotion of equitable English language education. This study thus aims to fill this gap in the literature on translanguaging.

Based on qualitative data elicited from semi-structured interviews and reflective journals collected from a university in southern China, this study

aims to analyse the extent to which students' beliefs and practices involve the notion of translanguaging and how translanguaging for equity can be realised in the English language classroom by answering the following two research questions:

1. How do students perform their language beliefs, language usage and identity construction when acquiring content knowledge through English?
2. To what extent, if any, do students pursue linguistic and epistemic equity by understanding and adopting translanguaging in their language usage?

3. Method

3.1. Context and participants

This study was conducted at a first-tier comprehensive university in southeast China. The university offers various EMI programmes in Business, Law, Journalism, Liberal Arts and Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) majors. An English enhancement programme is also highlighted at this university as an initiative to promote English proficiency and create an English learning environment. Students at the university need to attend both English language and EMI content courses. The student participants were all recruited as volunteers. The selection criteria were as follows: (1) all the participants should have experienced taking both English language and content courses, and (2) expressed willingness to participate in this study (cf. Creswell, 2009). All participants were either bilingual or multilingual and had passed the *College English Test Band 6* with an intermediate level of English proficiency (CEFR B2 to C1).

3.2. Data collection

In this study, data were collected via semi-structured interviews and reflective journals to examine the students' perceptions of, and practices concerning, translanguaging. The qualitative approach adopted in this study aimed to capture "the experiences and lived meanings of the subjects' everyday world" (Kvale, 2007, p. 11). The researchers also sought to elicit 'how' and 'why' aspects from the participants (Lune & Berg, 2017) to better showcase their language beliefs, language usage and identity construction in relation to their understanding of linguistic and epistemic equity through the use of translanguaging.

Ten students were invited to take part in the interview based on the purposive sampling research method (Cohen et al., 2018) (see Table 1) through telephone

calls and contact through social media. The interviews were conducted face-to-face or through *Tencent Meeting (Voov Meeting)*. Each interview lasted about 25-40 minutes. The semi-structured interviews focused on three topics: (1) language power and hierarchy, (2) language usage, and (3) language users and identity. In terms of ethical issues, all participants were guaranteed anonymity and confidentiality, and the students' names were not revealed in reporting the data. The interviews were conducted in Putonghua to ensure that the interviewees accurately understood the questions and expressed their views fully (Mann, 2011). With the consent of the interviewees, the interviews were recorded, transcribed verbatim, and translated into English. The translated texts were checked by a professor of translation and verified by the interviewees to make sure that the content of the translated interviews matched the source data in the original language. Each interviewee was then asked to check their transcribed text to ensure the accuracy of the transcription.

Table 1
Profile of Participants

Participant	Gender	School/college	Grade	English Level	Length of Interview
S1	M	College of Engineering	Year 2	B2	32' 16"
S2	F	School of Journalism	Year 1	B2	35' 19"
S3	F	College of Liberal Arts	Year 3	C1	26' 08"
S4	M	School of Journalism	Year 2	B2	32' 38"
S5	F	School of Law	Year 1	B2	29' 19"
S6	F	School of Business	Year 2	B2	35' 48"
S7	F	School of Science	Year 3	C1	30' 27"
S8	M	College of Liberal Arts	Year 1	B2	38' 29"
S9	F	School of Business	Year 2	B2	25' 14"
S10	F	School of Law	Year 3	C1	36' 22"

To triangulate the spoken data through semi-structured interviews, reflective journals were also written by the interviewees to investigate further whether they understood the concept of translanguaging and how they perceived the adoption of translanguaging in promoting linguistic and epistemic equity.

3.3. Data analysis

After the accuracy of the texts had been confirmed, qualitative content analysis of the interview data was conducted using *NVivo 12* software (Schreier, 2012). With the research questions in mind, the first round of coding from a top-down deductive approach obtained several major themes, including language power, language hierarchy, English only, translanguaging use, the use of other languages

and knowledge acquisition through EMI. Another round of bottom-up inductive coding helped the researchers identify the following three key themes for the purpose of data analysis in this paper: (1) language power and hierarchy, (2) monolingual or multilingual use, and (3) language users and identity. Moreover, the data in the reflective journals were described and interpreted under the topic of translanguaging and equity. For reporting purposes, rather than all the transcribed interactional sequences being presented, only the representative extracts associated with the identified topics were selected from the reflective journals.

4. Results

4.1. Language power and hierarchy

When asked for opinions on the existence of language power and hierarchy, some students (e.g., S1, S4, S3, S7, S8) were in disagreement with the concept and took an open-minded view towards languages, treating all of them fairly. However, despite the fact that both S1 and S4 considered all languages to be equal, they still appeared to have a preference for the exclusive use of English. They believed that English should be the main focus in the English language classroom and, therefore, its usage should be given priority.

Excerpt 1: I think language is for communication. All languages are tools. English and Chinese are not a hierarchical thing. It is just that in the English classroom, almost everyone naturally uses English, and thus you should give priority to the use of English or you are not following the crowd. But I think some people still think they are superior because they can speak English. Anyway, I am very tired of such people; I don't think it is necessary and fair. All languages matter. (S1)

Excerpt 2: I think English is indeed the preferred language for EMI courses. As I said earlier, this is sort of the default rule for EMI classes. Since you are in a much purer English-speaking community, or in the immersive English environment that EMI courses can provide, you should choose English as a priority. But I don't think English is superior to other languages. All languages are equal, I think. (S4)

Actually, these two students might have been influenced by the initial letter "E" in EMI courses, the qualifier "English" in English language education and anything else related to English; they tended to give the impression that the priority they gave to the English language had become firmly entrenched in their minds. Therefore, if stakeholders had not been adequately informed in advance about the significance of de-naturalising the hegemony of the English language and other forms of normativity, they might have perceived the

English language as the de-facto and preferred language in the English language classroom. Consequently, they would have favoured the exclusive use of English and marginalised the presence of other languages.

Some students expressed the belief that there exist power and hierarchy among languages. For instance, S2 considered English to be superior to Chinese and other languages in the EMI course. When providing reasons, she normalised the dominant position of English and linked it to universality in a globalised society.

Excerpt 3: First, I think EMI has historically promoted teaching in English, and thus in EMI courses, and improving the ability to use English is very important. The second reason is that most knowledge worldwide is now based on the English system, which is used to formulate entire teaching content and frameworks. So English is the most important and privileged language in EMI courses. (S2)

When asked to rank English, Chinese and other languages in the EMI course, S2's answer reflected the apparent linguistic inequality under the influence of the hegemony and universality of English, saying, "I will put English in first place in EMI courses. As for other languages, I'll decide how important they are based on how many people use those languages."

However, S7 distinguished the supremacy and superiority of a language from its universality. She pointed out that the broad use of a language such as English did not mean that it had more power and a higher status.

Excerpt 4: I think that languages used in EMI courses do not so much have a relationship of power and hierarchy as of universality and non-universality. English is a language for global use, so it must be universal, but you can't say universality means power. (S7)

S9, however, believed that the choice of adopting EMI itself reflects recognition of the language hierarchy.

Excerpt 5: I think the very fact that individuals want to choose EMI courses implies a hierarchical relationship among languages. Just because you think it will be better to learn English and also improve your English, you pick an EMI course. (S9)

Moreover, according to S9, the existence of an epistemological conflict can be inferred in relation to the symbolic power of language in students' minds, namely the powerful universality regarding traditional native English ideology with Anglophone cultures and the powerless non-universality of other

seemingly 'less useful' linguistic and cultural resources (Kramsch, 2020). The knowledge, languages, cultures and worldviews of the former are valued, accepted and privileged, while those of the later are underestimated, denied and marginalised.

Excerpt 6: There is such a hierarchy of power among languages, probably because of the degree to which a language is circulated. English, no matter how it is spoken, is an international language that is used globally. It is probably because English-speaking countries are developed countries. Now people appreciate and have a yearning for the culture and values of developed countries. From a global perspective, I think this is also a reason. (S9)

In addition, some students (e.g., S5, S6) were not aware of the existence of language power and hierarchy. S10 maintained a neutral stance towards language hierarchy and power, asserting that the existence of power relations depends on whether humans' value judgments are embedded in languages. Furthermore, she emphasized that teachers bear the primary responsibility for shaping students' attitudes towards languages and their usage.

Excerpt 7: I think it depends on how the teacher handles the use of language in the classroom when dealing with any hierarchical relationship among languages. If the teacher takes a negative attitude when the students use their native language in EMI courses, the students may feel uncomfortable and see it as biased. But if teachers adopt an inclusive approach that not only encourages the use of English but also allows and protects students' right to express themselves in their native language, I think it would be great. It's difficult to say anything about the power and hierarchy of language in EMI courses, as it depends on the teachers. Moreover, I think there is no such power relationship between languages, but if some people's value judgment were involved in languages, there might be a relationship between power and hierarchy. (S10)

In general, it appeared that numerous students held intricate attitudes towards the authority and hierarchy of languages. They were largely influenced by the naturalised hegemony of the English language and other prescribed types of normativity that were prevalent in EMI courses (Fang & Liu, 2020; Sah, 2022). Even those students who did not subscribe to such views could not help affirm the privileged and preferential status of the English language in EMI courses. In sum, it is essential to guide and transform stakeholders' perceptions of languages to understand that the use of English as the medium of instruction does not contradict or hinder the expression of other languages for meaning-

making. In EMI classrooms, a bilingual or even translingual approach for communication and meaning-making should be acknowledged, appreciated, and encouraged. As long as intelligibility is ensured, all languages are allowed to appear in EMI courses.

4.2. Monolingual or multilingual usage

As there is no explicit policy mandating the exclusive use of English in EMI courses, the language usage in classrooms can be intricate and ambiguous. When asked about their perspectives regarding the utilization of language in EMI courses, the majority of the students still expressed a preference for exclusive employment of the English language. However, their autonomy and individuality could be discerned through the translingual practices that resonate with translanguaging, particularly when it comes to fostering mutual comprehension and knowledge acquisition (Cenoz & Gorter, 2021).

According to most of the students, the use of language should be knowledge-orientated for content learning and individual-orientated for basic communication purposes. To be specific, when knowledge is accessible to almost all students, the monolingual use of English can be adopted to greatly help enhance their ability to use English. However, when knowledge becomes quite inaccessible to most students, the translingual or multilingual use of languages, as well as other practices responding to translanguaging, should be embraced in the classroom to help prioritise and promote all students' learning and acquisition of knowledge (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016).

Excerpt 8: The use of English alone can greatly improve your oral English proficiency. Besides, some concepts are hard to translate and understand in Chinese, so it might be better only to use English in EMI courses. However, the purpose of EMI courses is to gain knowledge better through the English language. Therefore, language is a tool and helps you to gain knowledge more efficiently. So, if you can learn knowledge more efficiently through other languages, why not? It is also fair to those of us who are not native English-speaking learners to involve more languages than English to absorb more knowledge. (S1)

Excerpt 9: I think that if the difficulty of the course content were acceptable, I would prefer teachers to teach in English. But if it's something I haven't been exposed to, I would choose to involve a little Chinese but mainly use English. Sometimes, I myself also switch to my native language during EMI courses when the teacher talks about a difficult concept, since I have to use Chinese to clarify and understand it. (S3)

Excerpt 10: Although I think the use of English is far superior to that of Chinese in EMI courses, I'm still flexible about changing my language usage, rather than sticking to English only in EMI courses because the primary purpose of EMI courses is to learn knowledge, not to adhere to any policy. (S6)

Excerpt 11: Because there is seldom such an opportunity to speak English, when you have acquired the knowledge, you can make use of a monolingual atmosphere for discussions in English. But I think specialised courses should be multilingual, while general courses can be only in English. That does not mean that specialised courses cannot be fully in English, but it is just that I need to preview them because the content might be hard to understand in English alone. (S8)

From the excerpts above, it can be seen that students grasped the importance of English in content learning, although they may have felt more at ease in acquiring content knowledge with the help of their L1 by maximising their linguistic repertoire in learning (Fang & Liu, 2020). In particular, in addition to focusing on multilingual resources, S5 also mentioned the use of multimodal and multi-semiotic resources to help offer more equal opportunities to gain knowledge in EMI classrooms, which involved the notion of translanguaging for equity.

Excerpt 12: Actually, I think language performance in EMI courses should be analysed on a case-by-case basis, rather than generalised. For example, at our university, not all students have the same level of English. In some classes, the English level of students may be very high, whereas in other classes, it may be a little lower. If EMI courses use English alone, it may be unfair to those students with lower English proficiency, since they cannot understand or master professional knowledge quickly in English. But it is also not desirable to speak entirely in Chinese, and doing so will not achieve the purpose of learning English in EMI courses. I think people can use visual aids such as *PowerPoint* or illustrations in English to present knowledge and then occasionally explain them in Chinese. Well, this is what I usually do in EMI lessons when I give a presentation to share knowledge, and I find it accessible for, and acceptable to, almost every student. I feel that EMI is more of an art. It's about getting the balance right to help all students learn knowledge and at the same time improve their English. (S5)

From the comments of S5, translanguaging strategy or practice is naturally embedded in students' linguistic performance in EMI courses, although she

also realised the importance of language planning through the use of translanguaging (even if she had not heard of the term).

4.3. Language users and identity

When the participants were asked how they viewed themselves and others in the process of using English or other languages in the EMI classroom, some of them (e.g., S1, S3, S4, S6, S8, S9) seemed to see themselves as language users with a Chinese identity or as intercultural or global citizens (Fang & Baker, 2018). The following excerpts indicated the students' usage of English in relation to their identity negotiation and construction.

Excerpt 13: I think English is just a tool. Everyone can use this tool to express themselves in EMI courses. I cannot understand why some people think English belongs exclusively to native English speakers. We don't learn English to become native English speakers; instead, we are just Chinese people using English for communication and learning. Furthermore, I think teachers and students should use whatever languages they want in EMI classrooms because no language has ownership when being used in different real situations. (S1)

Excerpt 14: I think that when languages other than English are used in EMI courses, I am more open-minded, and it makes me feel like I have a global identity. That is, I am not struggling to choose between my language and others or between English and others. We are just able to use any local or global languages for ourselves. We are all the same living in this world. (S3)

Excerpt 15: I feel like I am still who I am. I am still Chinese, no matter how much I use English or other languages. But I think that when more languages are involved in the classroom, it makes me feel as if I am in a cultural melting pot, and in that sense, I am more than just Chinese; I am part of the world. You know, it feels like we are participating in a global and multicultural environment. (S8)

It could be seen that translanguaging practice can enhance students' awareness of global citizen development, with their L1 an important resource to be recognised from their identity aspect. However, there were also students, such as S2 and S10, who believed their proficient use of English gave them a native speaker-like identity and a superior position. It could also be seen that such language ideology based on the use of English may be influenced by native-speakerism (Holliday, 2005), which regards anything related to native speakers as much more valuable and honourable.

Excerpt 16: You know, English is the most important and superior language in the world, and native speakers from the West generally speak excellent English. I think when I speak English fluently and perfectly in the classroom, it seems that I am becoming native-like, which gives me a sense of privilege. (S2)

Furthermore, S10 believed that receiving the recognition of native English speakers was a signal of becoming native-like and showed a preference for having native English speakers as model teachers for learning English.

Excerpt 17: Many lessons in the English Learning Centre are taught by international teachers. I think, if you want to learn a language well, you should choose a native English-speaking teacher. I think my English is fine, and I can pick up their courses. I feel like I have been admitted into the native English-speaking community when I receive praise from foreign teachers. I am also very interested in foreign teachers, the culture of the countries they come from and their different experiences. This is something that Chinese teachers do not have, since most of them live in a culture similar to ours, and at best, they have been abroad to study. So I think native English teachers have more right to speak than anyone else about the use of English in the classroom. (S10)

In sum, it was expected that students would engage naturally in various multimodal and multi-semiotic resources to help meaning-making in their linguistic performance in EMI courses to facilitate content learning and knowledge acquisition. We could identify the relationship between language usage and people's identity construction, although it was non-linear and nuanced. The use of translanguaging was perceived to empower both global citizenship and local identity, while the native English norm was still inherently rooted in people's minds as a yardstick to evaluate people's use of English. The negotiation of the translanguaging strategy in relation to the ideology of native-speakerism also reflected the fact that language is a symbolic power in various academic and social settings (Kramsch, 2020).

4.4. Translanguaging and equity

The interview findings revealed that not all students had fully developed a comprehensive and inclusive understanding of languages and language usage in relation to their identity. Many of the participants were still largely influenced by the hegemony of the English language, the culture and knowledge systems being biased towards the English language, the monolingual and prioritised use of English, and having a native English speaker identity (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2013). Translanguaging, as discussed above,

has the potential to help reduce inequality as manifested in language and knowledge learning in EMI classrooms. Therefore, to probe the availability and sustainability of translanguaging in the promotion of linguistic and epistemic equity in EMI classrooms, the reflective journals of the ten interviewees were obtained and analysed after they had learned of the concept of translanguaging (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2011).

In the reflective journals, six of the participants voiced that they had not previously heard of the notion of translanguaging. Although four of the participants mentioned that they had heard of the term, their understanding of translanguaging was largely limited to linguistic performances such as code-switching. Only one student mentioned that translanguaging involved interaction and communication that transcended general language symbols to include gestures and eye contact.

When it came to access to language and knowledge in English language education, almost all participants agreed that there was no absolute equity in approaching this issue. Most participants attributed linguistic and epistemic inequity to economic disparity and particularly the resource gap. They believed that the unequal distribution of resources in English language education is to blame. Therefore, they believed that the rational distribution and optimal utilisation of resources in English language education could contribute to achieving linguistic and epistemic fairness. S8 also related linguistic and epistemic inequality to language learners' own abilities and challenged the situation whereby some students who are not competent in a certain language (particularly English) fail to learn and acquire language and knowledge at a normal standard.

After the concept of translanguaging by Li (2018), namely that it is a dynamic process whereby learners flexibly use all kinds of linguistic, cognitive, semiotic and modal resources and create meanings, had been explained to them, all of the participants expressed their agreement that translanguaging can help promote language users' equal access to linguistic and epistemic equity. Various reasons were mentioned concerning why translanguaging can work as an approach to linguistic and epistemic equity. Some students (e.g., S1, S3, S6, S9) considered that, at the macro and micro levels, translanguaging promotes equality and inclusive education by breaking the shackles of uneven regional and economic development to focus on stakeholders involved in language education. Through the lens of the learning process, some students (e.g., S4, S5, S7) believed that translanguaging shows practicality, diversity and flexibility and goes beyond the use of languages to include multiple resources and means of meaning-making for use to a greater extent to ensure a much more comprehensive acquisition of knowledge and language. From the perspective of language users, S3 considered that translanguaging pays attention to the

development of flexible and individualised language learning and takes into account the differences among individuals and their communities, thereby contributing to their acquisition of language and knowledge. S7 believed that translanguaging mobilises the initiative of language learners, helps enhance their understanding of language and knowledge and effectively promotes the flow and sharing of different resources.

However, according to some students (e.g., S2, S10), translanguaging may also fail to meet the goal of reaching linguistic and epistemic equity with regard to some constraints, such as the abilities of teachers and students, the condition of the education infrastructure and the timing for the incorporation and integration of multiple resources. Some students (e.g., S3, S6, S9), who understood superficially or misunderstood the notion of translanguaging, also questioned the feasibility of translanguaging in promoting linguistic and epistemic equity. They regarded translanguaging to only be focused on aspects of languages, thereby only benefitting those students majoring in languages or over-amplifying linguistic disparities by giving an example of a lexical gap in the translation process.

Almost all participants believed that, in order to sustain the positive role of translanguaging in the promotion of linguistic and epistemic equity, the notion of translanguaging should be widely promoted and explained from the bottom up to inform language users of its true essence and meaning to avoid a unilateral interpretation. In this sense, they would be armed with translanguaging to effectively combat inequalities in language education. Some students (e.g., S1, S4, S7) also recommended that teachers be trained and well-prepared to raise awareness of translanguaging to help provide guidance for all students in acquiring language and knowledge (Yuan & Yang, 2023). Furthermore, other students called for more efforts to maintain the playfulness, flexibility, scientificity and comprehensibility embedded in the concept of translanguaging by arguing the need of incorporating various linguistic and semiotic resources in education and knowledge acquisition.

5. Discussion

The findings of the qualitative data partially and implicitly echo those of previous studies (e.g., Fang & Liu, 2020; Rafi & Morgan, 2022; Tai, 2022; Tai & Li, 2020; Tai & Wong, 2023) and argue for the instructive role teachers play in helping students pursue language and knowledge equity through translanguaging. In what follows, the discussion mainly focuses on analysing the understanding of translanguaging for equity from both the interviews and the reflective journal findings.

In terms of the first research question, the language beliefs, language practices and identity construction found in the interview data were manifested in a

complex manner; the students either viewed English as being at the top of the language pyramid or considered all languages equal but still had a tendency to prioritise English (Bacon & Kim, 2018; Baker & Hüttner, 2019; Heller, 2010). Students' language usage primarily relied on knowledge and involved either using only the English language or multiple languages along with other non-linguistic resources inclusively. The students constructed their identity in the process of language learning and knowledge acquisition as English language users from China, as intercultural/global citizens or as native-like English speakers (Boonsuk & Fang, 2023; Fang & Baker, 2018).

Regarding the second research question, the reflective journal data revealed the potential ways in which translanguaging can effectively involve all students in language learning and knowledge acquisition, considering the inequity present in the expressions of language beliefs, language practices, and identity construction found in the interview data. The full use of language learners' linguistic repertoires and resources was affirmed in this study, in line with both Fernández's (2019) and Suárez's (2020) studies, to help promote more equitable learning spaces for all students. However, the findings of Fernández's (2019) study were more focused on individuals and demonstrated a greater emphasis on providing humanistic care to culturally and linguistically diverse students. The study explored the concept of translanguaging and its role in empowering students to express their true selves and unleash their authority, agency, subjectivity, and creativity. The findings with regard to showing respect for the differences among individuals through the adoption of translanguaging were consistent with those of valuing all students' home languages, cultures and identities through translanguaging. Nevertheless, Suárez's (2020) study focused more on the practical level and presented the means of enhancing equal participation in learning supported by translanguaging. Echoing Suárez's (2020) argument, the findings of this study in the Chinese context also emphasise the need to incorporate other non-linguistic multimodal and trans-semiotic resources in the classroom setting along with the active use of students' linguistic resources.

However, from the interview data, the practice involving translanguaging for equal access to language and knowledge in this study still largely remained at the level of language, such as in multilingual usage, while it seldom took into consideration other multi-semiotic, multimodal and cognitive dimensions (only S5 mentioned the use of multimodal and multi-semiotic resources in her reflective journal). In this sense, this study notes that there was a considerable gap between ideally knowing how translanguaging functioned to promote linguistic and epistemic equity in theory and actually implementing translanguaging for equity in language education in practice (Fang et al., 2022; Li, 2022; Phyak, 2023). Therefore, this paper emphasizes the importance of cultivating a mindset that values treating all individuals, their language, and

their knowledge fairly. It also highlights the need for practical and inclusive utilisation of diverse linguistic and non-linguistic resources through pedagogical translanguaging to promote linguistic and epistemic equity, as well as social and academic participation in the classroom (García & Li, 2014; Liu et al., 2020; Muguruza et al., 2023).

6. Conclusion

The present study explored how the language beliefs, language practices, and identity construction of students unfolded in EMI classrooms and how translanguaging can be implemented to help all students obtain as much linguistic and epistemic equity as possible. According to the interview data, the language beliefs, language practices and identity construction of students were quite complex and reflected the inequalities hidden behind their acquisition of language and knowledge, which is a growing phenomenon under the hegemonic status of the English language as well as its cultural and knowledge system (Fang & Dovchin, 2022; Phyak & De Costa, 2021). However, it could also be noticed that among students' different language beliefs, language usage and identity construction, there was an opportunity to infuse translanguaging into EMI classrooms (Fang & Liu, 2020). In consideration of the existence of some students' inclusive views on all languages, their inclusive practices involved multiple meaning-making resources as well as their identity positioning towards more inclusive and supra-ethnic identities, such as being a local actor equipped with international awareness (Fang & Xu, 2022; Rees & Williams, 2017).

Moreover, the reflective journal data went on to reveal the extent to which translanguaging could be incorporated into the promotion of equitable English language education from the perspective of students. As shown in the analysis, the students mentioned that translanguaging could succeed in enhancing more equal access to language and knowledge through the inclusion of multiple linguistic and non-linguistic resources for comprehension and meaning-making as well as the respect for the subjectivities of, and differences among, individuals and their communities. Therefore, this study highlights how translanguaging creates an inclusive space for facilitating equity in language learning and knowledge construction by giving voices to the student groups. It also suggests that more concerted efforts should be made to raise awareness of translanguaging among both teachers and students, since the notion of translanguaging still seems to be far from becoming widely acknowledged and accurately grasped.

However, since relevant studies of translanguaging for equity are scarce and this study mainly focuses on bi/multilingual students taking EMI courses at a university in the Chinese context, a more dedicated account of other student

populations would contribute further to this field. In this way, more insight into, and understanding of, the role of translanguaging and more effective ways for it to sustain linguistic and epistemic equity could be gained to provide more references and implications for the development of equitable English language education. As an important ‘washback’, à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021b), of this study, we voice an urgent need to gather more instances of translanguaging in shaping and constructing language and knowledge learning that is available and accessible to all students in various bi/multilingual educational contexts.

Notes:

1. For other relevant topics including multilingualism, diversity, equity, social justice, activism, and so forth, please see Balosa (2024), Chaka (2024), Hannaford and Alexander (2024), Huang (2024), Kruger-Marias (2024), Mapuya (2024), Motaung (2024), Ndlangamandla (2024), Ndlangamandla et al. (2024), and Nkhi and Shange (2024).

Authors’ Statement

The authors discussed and conceived the article together. Yidie Xu contributed to the writing of the draft. Fan Fang contributed to background research and overall idea development, as well as writing and editing the second draft of this paper. Both authors contributed to the revision process of this paper.

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